

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF COMPLEX METALLIC FERRO AND FERRICYANIDES. PART VII. CONDUCTOMETRIC STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF CADMIUM FERRICYANIDE

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The composition of cadmium ferricyanide has been studied by the conductometric titrations of cadmium sulphate solution with potassium ferricyanide solution. The titrations have been made by the direct and the reverse methods, in aqueous and aqueous-alcoholic media. The composition arrived at approximates to $\text{KCd}_{10}(\text{FeCy}_6)_7$.

The conductometric titration arrangement was similar to the one used previously (Bhattacharya and Gaur, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 25, 27). Potassium ferricyanide solution was prepared by direct weighing and estimated by titrating against standardised solution of sodium thiosulphate (Treadwell and Hall, "Analytical Chemistry", Vol. II, p. 590). In view of the isomeric modifications of potassium ferricyanide (Getman, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1921, 25, 147) the anhydrous, ruby-red α -compound was used throughout these investigations. The solution was kept, as far as possible, free from organic reducing matter and shielded from daylight. Cadmium sulphate solution was estimated by the electrolytic method (Vogel, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", p. 611).

Using different concentrations of the solutions of cadmium sulphate and potassium ferricyanide, the titrations were carried out by the direct and reverse methods, *i.e.*, when cadmium sulphate from the burette was added to potassium ferricyanide taken in the cell, and *vice versa*. The titrations were also carried out in alcoholic medium up to a total concentration of 20% by volume.

As potassium ferricyanide is a strong oxidising agent, it is necessary to ascertain that the changes in the observed titre values are not due to the partial reduction of potassium ferricyanide by alcohol. Control experiments were therefore carried out, and potassium ferricyanide solution containing 10% and 20% alcohol was estimated against standardised sodium thiosulphate solution. It was observed that inspite of its strong oxidising action, the reduction of potassium ferricyanide solution in presence of alcohol did not take place to any measurable extent in neutral medium, at room temperature, up to a period of one hour. Experiments show that there is practically no reduction even on boiling a 20% solution of potassium ferricyanide of strengths $M/5$ and $M/10$ on a water-bath for about 5 minutes. The observations are recorded below.

Similar titrations were carried out with $M/10$ and $M/50$ solutions of potassium ferricyanide, and no appreciable change in the observed titre values of potassium ferricyanide in presence of 10% and 20% alcohol was observed.

$M/4.82$ -solution of cadmium sulphate would be referred as $A/1$ - CdSO_4 solution

and $M/5.07$ solution of potassium ferricyanide would be referred as A/1-ferricyanide solution.

TABLE I

Strength of the solution = $M/5$

Vol. of K_3FeCy_6 soln. (v)	Alcohol added.	Time.	Obsd. titre values of $N/10-Na_2S_2O_3$ soln. for 'v' c.c. of K_3FeCy_6 soln.	Calc. titre value for 20 c.c. of K_3FeCy_6 soln.	Theo. titre value.
20 c.c.	Nil		20.05 c.c.	20.05 c.c.
18	2 c.c.	Immediate	18.05	20.06 c.c.	...
"	"	15 min.	18.05	20.06	...
"	"	30	18.05	20.06	...
"	"	1 hr.	18.05	20.06	...
16	4	Immediate	16.05	20.06	20.05
"	"	15 min.	16.05	20.06	...
"	"	30	16.05	20.06	...
"	"	1 hr.	16.05	20.06	...
"	"	Boiled	16.0	20.0	...

TABLE II

Results obtained by direct conductometric titrations

A/1- $CdSO_4$ and A/10- K_3FeCy_6 . Conc. ratio (n) = 10:1

A/10- K_3FeCy_6 in the cell (v).	Alcohol added.	$CdSO_4$ reqd. for 'v' c.c. A/10- K_3FeCy_6 in the cell (v_1).	$CdSO_4$ for 10 c.c. A/10- K_3FeCy_6 (v_1/v) ₁₀	Equiv. vol. of A/10- $CdSO_4$ $n'(v_1/v)$ ₁₀	Curve No.
10 c.c.	0.0 c.c.	1.37 c.c.	1.37 c.c.	13.7 c.c.	1
9	1.0	1.22	1.36	13.6	2
8	2.0	1.07	1.34	13.4	3

A/2- $CdSO_4$ and A/10- K_3FeCy_6 . Conc. ratio (n) = 5:1

10 c.c.	0.0 c.c.	2.76 c.c.	2.76 c.c.	13.80 c.c.	4
9	1.0	2.46	2.73	13.65	5
8	2.0	2.16	2.70	13.50	6

TABLE III

Results obtained by reverse conductometric titrations.

<i>A/2-K₃FeCy₆ and A/10-CdSO₄. Conc. ratio (n) = 5:1</i>					
<i>A/10-CdSO₄ in the cell (v).</i>	<i>Alcohol added.</i>	<i>K₃FeCy₆ reqd. for CdSO₄ in the cell (v₁).</i>	<i>K₃FeCy₆ calc. for 10 c.c. A/10-CdSO₄ (v₁/v)₁₀</i>	<i>Equiv. vol. of A/10- K₃FeCy₆ n(v₁/v)₁₀.</i>	<i>Curve No.</i>
10 c.c.	0.0 c.c.	1.35 c.c.	1.35 c.c.	6.75 c.c.	7
9.0	1.0	1.24	1.38	6.90	8
8.0	2.0	1.16	1.45	7.25	9
<i>A/4-K₃FeCy₆ and A/10-CdSO₄. Conc. ratio (n) = 2.5:1</i>					
10.0 c.c.	0.0 c.c.	2.74 c.c.	2.74 c.c.	6.85 c.c.	10
9.0	1.0	2.50	2.78	6.95	11
8.0	2.0	2.32	2.90	7.25	12

DISCUSSION

In continuation of our previous studies on the composition of copper and cadmium ferrocyanides (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **25**, 487, 499; 1948, **25**, 27, 185, 191, 220) we observe that the composition of cadmium ferricyanide leads to more interesting observations as the composition is of a different order than those of copper and cadmium ferrocyanides. From the strengths of the solutions of cadmium sulphate (*M/4.82*) and potassium ferricyanide (*M/5.07*), the theoretical titre values for 10 c. c. of potassium ferricyanide solution for the formation of the compounds KCdFeCy_6 , $\text{Cd}_3(\text{FeCy}_6)_2$ and $\text{KCd}_{10}(\text{FeCy}_6)_7$; in direct titrations are 9.5, 14.25 and 13.5 c.c. respectively of the cadmium sulphate solution. The theoretical titre values for 10 c.c. of cadmium sulphate solution for the formation of the same compounds in the reverse titrations are respectively 10.52, 7.01 and 7.37 c.c. of ferricyanide solution.

The observed titre values in the direct and reverse titrations can be said to approximate the theoretical titre values for the formation of the compounds $\text{Cd}_3(\text{FeCy}_6)_2$ and $\text{KCd}_{10}(\text{FeCy}_6)_7$. The possibility of the formation of the compound KCdFeCy_6 is ruled out on the basis of the conductometric results.

The observed titre values for 10 c.c. of potassium ferricyanide solution in aqueous medium is 13.7 to 13.8 c.c. of cadmium sulphate solution. In presence of increasing amounts of alcohol the observed titre values decrease, and almost approach the theoretical titre value for the formation of the compound $\text{KCd}_{10}(\text{FeCy}_6)_7$. In view of the influence of hydrolysis upon such complexes (*loc. cit.*) it is expected that the observed titre values in the direct titrations in aqueous medium would be higher than the theoretical titre values, because the ferricyanide, released as a result of the hydrolysis, would consume some amount of cadmium sulphate solution. In presence of increasing

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

amounts of alcohol the hydrolysis would be checked to some extent, and so the observed titre values would then approach the theoretical titre value more closely. From these considerations it is obvious that the compound $\text{Cd}_2(\text{FeCy}_6)_2$ is not formed, because the observed titre values in aqueous medium (13.7 to 13.8) in direct titrations is lower than the theoretical titre value required for its formation, and in presence of increasing amounts of alcohol the discrepancy between the observed and the theoretical titre values for the same compound increases still more. The observations therefore support the formation of the compound $\text{KCd}_{10}(\text{FeCy}_6)_7$.

From similar considerations of the influence of hydrolysis, the titre values in aqueous medium would be lower than the theoretical titre values in the reverse titrations, i.e., when cadmium sulphate is taken in the cell and potassium ferricyanide is added from the burette, which in presence of increasing amounts of alcohol would increase. This is actually observed (*vide* Table II).

The nature of the discrepancies between the theoretical and observed titre values in the case of cadmium ferricyanide is similar to that observed in the case of cadmium ferrocyanide (*cf.* Parts IV and VI). The discrepancy in the case of cadmium ferricyanide

is, however, of a smaller magnitude. This shows that the influence of hydrolysis on the composition of the ferrocyanides is comparatively great than on the ferricyanides. This is also understood from the fact that ferricyanic acid is a stronger acid than the ferrocyanic acid, and hence the former forms stabler compounds than the latter.

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

The adsorption of Cd^{++} and $(FeCy_6)^{--}$ by the precipitated complex should also affect the observed titre values. In the reverse titrations cadmium sulphate being in the cell, the titrations are carried out in presence of excess of cadmium sulphate, and hence the chances of adsorption of Cd^{++} ions are greater. Therefore its effect in aqueous medium would be to lower the observed titre values than the theoretical titre value, and in presence of alcohol, a slight increase in the observed titre values will take place because of less adsorption in the alcoholic medium. The contrary observations in the titre values in the direct titrations suggest that the discrepancies between the observed and

the theoretical titre values are due to slightly greater adsorption of Cd^{++} ions by the precipitated complex than the $(\text{FeCy}_6)^{--}$ ions.

Experiments on hydrolysis, and of adsorption of Cd^{++} and $(\text{FeCy}_6)^{--}$ ions by cadmium ferricyanide sol are in progress and will be communicated in a subsequent communication.

Thus, on the basis of the conductometric study, it can be concluded that cadmium ferricyanide corresponds to $\text{KCd}_{10}(\text{FeCy}_6)_7$, and it is stabler than the corresponding ferrocyanide (Parts IV, V and VI).

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